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Yaw-steering for CAIRT

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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p>In this note, we investigate a satellite-position-dependent adjustment of the viewing yaw angle (“yaw steering law”). This adaptation is introduced to optimize and maximize the number of intersecting limb views required for tomographic retrievals. The optimization aims to align the center of the backward-looking observation track such that, in an Earth-fixed reference frame, the limb views lie within a common plane and are symmetrically distributed at the outer edges of the across-track swath.</p>		
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Document Control

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1.0	12.12.2023	First draft
2.0	14.12.2023	added more plots (zoom, altitude/latitude, yaw-definition) & inclusion of retrieval grid & inclusion of min/max latitude coverage
3.0	16.01.2024	The yaw viewing direction in v1 and v2 of this document already assumed a view pointing backwards towards the previous position of the satellite in the Earth-fixed coordinate system. I.e. slightly out of the orbital plane. In v3, a new (the first case) is introduced with the satellite pointing in the absolute orbital plane & Figure quality improvement & add plot of yaw-correction & Figures by Alex Hoffmann for better illustration of symbols etc.
4.0	24.01.2024	Added plots for yaw-correction provided by ESA
5.0	10.12.2024	Added plots for yaw-correction by ESA
6.0	10.10.2025	Implemented comments by Alex Hoffmann ESA on v4.

Signature by issuing authority and/or lead author

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1 Introduction

In this note, we investigate a satellite-position-dependent adjustment of the viewing yaw angle. This adaptation is introduced to optimize and maximize the number of intersecting limb views required for tomographic retrievals. The optimization aims to align the center of the backward-looking observation track such that, in an Earth-fixed reference frame, the limb views lie within a common plane and are symmetrically distributed at the outer edges of the across-track swath.

In more detail:

To facilitate along-track 2D tomographic retrievals, the line-of-sight of any spectral radiance measurement should ideally lie in the same (vertical) plane as consecutive along-track tangent points. Due to the geometry of the problem, this can only be achieved to a certain extent, and the associated requirement is set for the centre line-of-sight (LOSc), for which a vertical plane can be defined.

If LOSc were to be maintained within the orbital plane, Earth's rotation would move consecutive tangent points out of the vertical plane that contains LOSc, further leading to strong asymmetry horizontally across the FoV. This effect varies with latitude along the orbit; it is most pronounced at equatorial latitudes.

To improve alignment, a slowly varying azimuth adjustment needs to be implemented to compensate for Earth's rotation, in spacecraft coordinates referred to as a "yaw steering law". This slow variation in across-track pointing should be such as to minimise the angular deviation between the plane containing LOSc and the plane containing the consecutive tangent points. In other words, the distance of subsequent tangent points from the plane containing LOSc at time t_0 shall be minimised.

2 Calculation/plotting baselines

- For satellite position, the "METOP-B" orbit was applied using pyorbital. This includes the rotation of the Earth, i.e. the latitude/longitude from this module are the coordinates of the Earth-system (rotating with the Earth).
- assume that the 'yaw'-axis in Figure 27 is perpendicular to the 'H' plane in Figure 28
- across-track: Earth-following round view (i.e. constant pitch (=elevation) angle when changing azimuth (=yaw) – viewing direction for the different tracks
- assumption of 9 across-track views each 50 km wide (uneven number to show a central track)
- each 20th view plotted (distance 1000 km)
- central (orange) and the extreme tracks to both sides (green and blue)
- solid lines are the ray-paths for 5 km tangent altitude up to 130 km
- the tangent points at 5, 50, 120 km are shown as stars (5 km), squares (60 km), triangles (120 km)
- red crosses are the position of the satellite
- small dots indicate the retrieval grid (tangent point locations at 5 km altitude); each 2nd point along-track (distance 100 km) and each point across-track (50 km distance) plotted
- see Figure 2 - Figure 4 for illustration of plots
- Earth-shape is assumed spherical ($r = 6367.4429$ km)

3 Backward view within orbital plane

- looking exactly 180° with respect to the flight direction (backward view in orbital plane)

Conclusions from Figure 1 - Figure 7:

- strong deviation of azimuth viewing direction from retrieval grid especially at equatorial latitudes.
- the minimum/maximum latitude range of the tangent point retrieval grid would be -83.0° - $+83.0^{\circ}$

Figure 1

Figure 2 Along-track altitude-latitude view of the right track in Figure 1.

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5 Zoom of Figure 1.

Figure 6 Zoom of Figure 1.

Figure 7 Zoom of Figure 1.

4 Backward view towards previous lat/lon position rotating with Earth

- Looking into the backward direction towards the last position of the satellite in lat/lon fixed Earth coordinate system (i.e. rotating)

Conclusions from Figure 8 - Figure 11:

- central track is not viewing at its own track but +-1 one track across (for the extreme points of the line-of-sight at 130 km)
- lines-of-sight of the outermost tracks view up to +-4 track-widths across into the planes of the neighbouring tracks
- the minimum/maximum latitude range of the tangent point retrieval grid would be $-82.2^\circ - +82.2^\circ$, therefore violating MATER requ. MR-1060 on 'spatial (latitude) coverage' which requires $+83^\circ$

Figure 8 Same as Figure 1 but with viewing towards the last position of the satellite in fixed lat/lon Earth system.

Figure 9 Zoom of Figure 8.

Figure 10 Zoom of Figure 8.

Figure 11 Zoom of Figure 8.

5 Backward view towards previous lat/lon position rotating with Earth and additional yaw-correction

To produce a symmetric picture with maximum overlap for tomography and not too large extrapolation needed for outermost pixels, a parametric correction (chi-by-eye-optimization of the symmetric view and the parallel line-of-sights of the central tracks.) of the yaw (Figure 27) viewing angle is introduced:

$$\text{yaw}_{\text{ori}} = \text{yaw}_{\text{flightdirection}} + 180^\circ \quad (\text{yaw}_{\text{flightdirection}} = 0, \text{ or equal to the azimuth angle in flight direction})$$

$$\text{yaw}_{\text{new}} = \text{yaw}_{\text{ori}} + \text{yaw}_{\text{corr}}(\text{lat}_{\text{tang}})$$

with

$$\text{yaw}_{\text{corr}} = 4^\circ \times \sin(\text{lat}_{\text{tang}})$$

where

lat_{tang} = latitude of the tangent point at 50 km altitude

(yaw_{corr} increases in anti-clock-wise direction, different than in Figure 27!)

Conclusions from Figure 12 - Figure 15:

- no across-track viewing of central track
- maximum across-track view of outermost tracks to less than +2 tracks across
- the minimum/maximum latitude range of the tangent point retrieval grid would be $-84^\circ - +84^\circ$, in accordance with MATER requ. MR-1060 on 'spatial (latitude) coverage' which requires $+83^\circ$

Figure 12 Same as Figure 8 but with additional (sin) yaw-correction.

Figure 13 Zoom of Figure 12.

Figure 14 Zoom of Figure 12.

Figure 15 Zoom of Figure 12.

6 Yaw-correction provided by ESA, January 2024

A formula for yaw-correction has been provided by ESA (email, Alex Hoffmann 22-Jan-2024, 20:16):

$$\text{yaw} = \text{yawAngle} * (1 - (\text{lat}/\text{latMax})^2)^{0.5} * (\text{center_LOSz});$$

$$\text{yaw} = \text{yaw-correction}$$

$$\text{yawAngle} = 4\text{deg}$$

lat = latitude of the central LOS tangent point (here 50 km tangent altitude has been assumed)

$$\text{latMax} = 83\text{deg}$$

centerLOSz (Figure 16) is the z component of the line-of-sight in ECEF [1].

Figure 16

Figure 17 Same as Figure 1 but with ESA's yaw-correction.

Figure 18 Zoom of Figure 17.

Figure 19 Zoom of Figure 17.

Figure 20 Zoom of Figure 17.

7 Yaw-correction provided by ESA, December 2024

A formula for yaw-correction has been provided by ESA (email, Fabric Boquet 10-Dec-2024):

$$\text{yaw} = a \cdot \sin(u + u_0)$$

With $a = 3.97 \text{deg}$

And $u_0 = 216 \text{deg}$,

u being the argument of latitude i.e. $u = w + v$

w = argument of perigee

v = true anomaly.

For implementation here, a csv-file (satLatAltYaw) was provided containing the following data per column over one full orbit with yaw steering :

- time (sec)
- satellite latitude (deg)
- satellite altitude (km)
- yaw (deg)

Without yaw steering, yaw is simply always equal to 0.

As can be seen from Figure 25, this correction is very similar to our ones proposed in chapter 4 but does not need the actual tangent point location. Its performance is also very similar as can be seen by comparing Figure 21 - Figure 24 to Figure 15.

Figure 21 Same as Figure 1 but with ESA 10-Dec-2024 yaw-correction.

Figure 22 Same as Figure 1 but with ESA 10-Dec-2024 yaw-correction.

Figure 23 Same as Figure 1 but with ESA 10-Dec-2024 yaw-correction.

Figure 24 Same as Figure 1 but with ESA 10-Dec-2024 yaw-correction.

8 Yaw-correction visualisation

Figure 25 Yaw correction as described in chapter 4 (blue), chapter 5 (orange) chapter 6 (green) and chapter 6 (red) compared to in-orbit-plane viewing (chapter 3). The arrows describe the flying-direction of the satellite.

Figure 26 Same as Figure 25 but vs time.

9 Definition of observational geometry

Figure 27 Definition of angles (from UCM-slide 45).

Figure 28 Definition of observational plane for the applied (KOPRA) viewing calculations.